

Need for reducing groundwater contamination through improved on-site sanitation facilities and framework

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Abstract : On-site sanitation and groundwater usage are prevalent and increasingly adopted in rapidly growing urban areas owing to the high cost involved in conventional sewerage network. However, the adsorption of on-site sanitation system puts the groundwater resources in the vicinity of the system at a greater risk. Microbial contaminants as well as chemical contaminants like nitrate are generated from human waste which travel through the medium and ultimately get in contact with the groundwater. Hence, the groundwater sources near the on-site sanitation systems are vulnerable to nitrate and bacterial contamination. Disease risks from drinking water infected with faecal coli and viral contaminants include hepatitis, poliomyelitis, diarrhoeal diseases, typhoid, dysentery and cholera. The present paper reviews the existing literature to reveal the knowledge gaps that could be addressed to improve the management of groundwater contamination from on-site sanitation. The contaminants associated with on-site sanitation namely microbiological and chemical, were analysed in two different geological settings namely Bhopal and Indore. The study revealed significant nitrate contamination in groundwater samples collected close to on-site sanitation systems. The study indicated seasonal variation in bacterial and nitrate contamination. More contamination was encountered in monsoon as compared to summer season. The results of the study alongwith existing literature emphasises the need to make better-informed decisions to protect water quality and safeguard human health. The paper also highlights a need to empirically test the effectiveness of specific guidelines under a variety of conditions in order to have better sanitation facility and to reduce realistic groundwater threats.

Keywords : On-site sanitation, groundwater quality, microbial contaminants, nitrate contamination, faecal coliform, Managing Groundwater Quality.

Introduction

Many people in the country rely upon untreated groundwater supplies for drinking water. These supplies are obtained from drilled boreholes or tubewells and dugwells. However, groundwater can become contaminated and there is special concern that the introduction of on-site sanitation systems may in certain circumstances contribute to contamination of drinking water supplies. The sewerage systems used successfully to provide adequate sanitation are more expensive to be set up. In rural and poor urban areas, where there is no possibility of laying the sewerage system in the near future, on-site sanitation is the preferred method of excreta and wastewater disposal. This is done by connecting the latrine (s) to a tank with a sub-soil dispersion system or a leaching pit. Where the soil is

not suitable for local dispersion of the effluent from the tank, the effluent could be collected in a connecting tank and the contents are periodically removed by means of a vacuum car or other means and disposed of in nearby drain.

The absence of centralized water supply leads people to depend on groundwater sources like bore-well, hand-pumps, and open wells to meet their drinking and domestic requirements. In view of the water being used for potable purpose, it is desirable that the impact of on-site sanitation system on groundwater quality be assessed and the maintenance of its quality through proper intervention ensured. The groundwater contamination from on-site sanitation system vis-à-vis geological settings has been dealt by different workers since the 1980s. The hydro-

geological factors, i.e. depth to water table, nature of the soil matrix, and lateral separation between the on-site sanitation and groundwater source are the key parameters affecting groundwater pollution^{1,2}. While the resource protection entails the assessment of aquifer vulnerability and pollutant loading at the scale of an aquifer, the source protection requires the best practice measures that can be realistically implemented around water source points.

Contamination from on-site sanitation can reach groundwater supplies by a range of pathways. The impact of on-site sanitation on the groundwater and surface sources has been dealt by various workers from time to time. The groundwater quality is deteriorated due to geogenic as well as anthropogenic factors. Among the anthropogenic factors, the impact of on-site sanitation on groundwater quality has been a subject of much concern. The contamination of groundwater due to on-site sanitation systems has been reported in many studies^{1,2,3-12}. 25% of all housing units in the USA have on-site sanitation systems¹³ and are reported to be source of local and regional groundwater contamination in USA^{13,14}. Studies carried out by Lawrence *et al.*¹ show the role of hydrogeology in the contamination of groundwater from on-site sanitation. The majority of the field studies have been confined, mainly to fine-grained sediments, which are of low risk, and consequently most suitable for on-site sanitation. There is a need to obtain more information on other soil types. There is a need for a classification of hydro-geological environments in relation to pollution risk. This would be of great value in the appraisal and implementation of on-site sanitation schemes.

Impact of on-site sanitation on groundwater :

Groundwater constitutes 97% of all freshwater that is potentially available for human use¹. Groundwater is therefore of fundamental importance to human life. In its natural state, groundwater is usually of good microbiological quality and is the preferred source of drinking water¹⁵. In urban settings, the on-site sanitation systems adopted can pose a significant adverse impact on the groundwater in the long run. On-site sanitation systems can lead to contamination of groundwater sources. The contamination takes place in the event of a pathway existing between a source i.e. on-site sanitation system and a recep-

tor i.e. groundwater body (Fig. 3). Fortunately, many contaminants, especially the micro-organisms are rendered harmless or reduced to low concentrations by natural processes when the movement of the contaminants in the sub-surface is slow. Maximisation of effluent residence times in the unsaturated zone is the key factor affecting the removal and elimination of bacteria and viruses¹⁶. Concern about groundwater pollution due to on-site sanitation system relates primarily to unconfined and, to a lesser degree, to semi-confined aquifers. If groundwater supplies are drawn from deep and confined aquifers, on-site sanitation does not pose a significant hazard. The usual means by which effluents affect drinking-water supplies is through pollution of groundwater that feeds wells and boreholes. A further danger is when effluent infiltrates the ground at shallow depth near to water pipes in which there is intermittent flow or in which at times the pressure is very low. Just as poor joints, cracks and holes in the pipe walls allow water to leak out when the pipes are full, so effluent leaks into the pipes when they are empty or under reduced pressure. In view of the dominant role of the hydro-geological characteristics in groundwater contamination, a proper evaluation will facilitate decision making for installation of on-site sanitation systems. Improper design, construction, operation or maintenance of on-site sanitation systems can lead to failure due to the loss of infiltration capacity, with consequent surfacing of effluent. Such failures are obvious, and are quite frequently reported. This can occur in certain hydro-geological conditions and may result in severe pollution of groundwater. It assumes more importance when the geological settings favour migration of the contaminants. A key determinant of risk variation is the soil and geological setting. Especially for consolidated hard rock sediments with poor soil cover and shallow water tables, the risk is higher. The problem can become alarming especially when the groundwater table is shallow and the unsaturated zone has fractures and fissures in it. In this background, it becomes essential to monitor the quality of groundwater in the vicinity of the on-site sanitation systems.

The factors affecting the pollution of groundwater are well documented^{11,17,8}. The major factors involved are as follows : (i) Depth of the water table – The chances of contamination increase significantly in geological settings

where the water table is very shallow i.e. between 1m–15m. (ii) The unsaturated zone – Soil provides a very effective natural treatment system by retarding the movement of faecal microorganism and chemical compounds towards the saturated zone. The nature of the geological strata and thickness of the unsaturated zone determine risk of pollution. The rock type and presence of fractures, are key factors in assessing vulnerability of aquifer to pollution. (iii) Effluent residence time in the unsaturated zone. The natural treatment processes, such as filtration, are more efficient in fine-grained unstructured soils. Structures such as root channels, animal burrows, natural voids and fissures commonly lead to short-circuiting of the natural treatment system with consequent reduction in residence time in the unsaturated zone. This may lead to greater risk of groundwater pollution. (iv) Clogging of the filtration surface in the latrine pit enhances bacteria and virus removal processes so that the risk of pollution diminishes after the first 100 days or so of pit usage. (v) More specifically, the risk of microbiological groundwater pollution will be minimal where more than 2 m of fine

unsaturated soils are present beneath the latrine pit, provided the hydraulic loading in the pit does not exceed 50 mm/day. (vi) In the saturated zone, pollutants move with the groundwater causing a pollution plume to develop from the pollution source. Contamination removal processes take place in the saturated zone but at a lesser rate compared to unsaturated zone since groundwater moves more rapidly. Within the saturated zone, dispersion and dilution play an important role in reducing the concentration of the contaminants.

Fortunately many of the contaminants do not flow far with the water. Microbiological contaminants are quickly filtered out as the water flows through the soil, and many chemical contaminants are absorbed onto the soil particles. So in general the further away from the source of contamination, the lower the concentration of contaminants is likely to be. According to WHO criteria¹⁸, if the above travel time is less than 25 days, there is significant risk to contamination; low risk, if the travel time is between 25 and 50 days; and very low risk if the travel time is greater than 50 days. The generally accepted minimum

Effect of borehole design on travel time and pathogen attenuation efficiency where on-site sanitation is practised (Source – British Geological Survey, 2001).

separation for pollution source and groundwater supply is equivalent to 50 days travel time (British Geological Survey, 2001). This is based on survival times of faecal indicator bacteria and viruses from laboratory and field experiments. The diagram shows the results for two borewell designs in the same shallow water-table aquifer; the separation distance for the shallow design would be unacceptable because the travel time is only a few days, and a design with a deeper screen is acceptable as the travel time is more.

Experimental

Sampling :

The groundwater samples were collected, stored and analysed for assessment of physico-chemical and bacteriological quality of water as per the “Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater” published by the American Public Health Association (APHA)¹⁹, the American Water Works Association (AWWA), and the Water Environment Federation (WEF) : 20th edition (1998). The samples were collected in summer and monsoon seasons.

Monitoring to establish cause of contamination :

The contamination of groundwater is dependent on a number of factors. Broadly, the factors are local hydrogeological characteristics like depth to water table, porosity and permeability of underlying strata. It is dependent to a large extent on the type of porosity i.e. whether it is primary porosity or secondary porosity. On-site systems often represent a significant hazard to groundwater because faecal matter accumulates in one place and leaching of associated microbiological and chemical contaminants into the sub-surface environment may occur. The majority of pathogens that affect humans are derived from faeces and transmitted by the oral route through a variety of ways including food, water, poor personal hygiene and flies. Therefore to reduce the health burden caused by infectious disease, interventions are required in excreta disposal, water supply and hygiene education. The principal chemical contaminant of concern is nitrate, the potential long-term impact of this contamination should be borne in mind when planning sanitation programmes as remedial action is difficult. The contamination derived from on-site sanitation in most rural areas impact ground-

water supplies in the immediate area but in larger villages and within urban settlements, where there may be many installations within a small area, there may be widespread contamination of the aquifer.

Sampling locations :

Bhopal :

Hydrogeology – In general the topography around the city of Bhopal is undulating with hills formed by Vindhyan formations and valleys occupied by alluvium and basalts²⁰. The hard-rocks underneath the top-soil cover, are the basalts and they constitute the aquifer. The aquifer has only secondary porosity in the form of fractures and joints. The fractures and joints are the potential pathways for migration of contaminants.

Sample collection and analysis : Groundwater samples were collected from Bhopal and analysed for nitrate and bacteriological contamination. Figs. 1, 2, 3 and 4 depict the range of the nitrate and faecal coliforms for Kainchi Chola and Karod respectively for summer and monsoon

Fig. 1. Nitrate concentration in groundwater samples of Karod, Bhopal.

Fig. 2. Faecal coliform concentration in groundwater samples of Karod, Bhopal.

seasons. The values for, nitrate and faecal coliforms showed large variation in both the seasons. In Karod, nitrate values were within the permissible limit in summer. In Karod, the sampling locations were scattered around the community septic tank. Nitrate values were within the permissible limit in summer and monsoon. All the samples were contaminated with faecal coliforms with maximum contamination noticed in monsoon. Faecal coliforms contamination was also found in samples collected during summer.

The overall study in Karod showed the presence of faecal coliforms in water samples located at a considerable distance from the community septic tank. The sources are all bore wells and hence presence of faecal coliforms in those samples can be attributed to the community septic tank. In Kainchi Chola, nitrate values for all the samples were within the desirable limit in summer (Fig. 3). All the samples were found to be contaminated with faecal coliforms in summer as well as in monsoon with maxi-

Fig. 3. Nitrate concentration in groundwater samples of Kainchi Chola, Bhopal.

Fig. 4. Faecal coliform concentration in groundwater samples of Kainchi Chola, Bhopal.

mum contamination found in monsoon.

Indore :

Hydrogeology – The Deccan Traps, which are the predominant rocks in the district, have wide variation in the water bearing properties of the different units constituting them. The massive basalts their weathered zones and secondary porosities and the vesicular basalts with their minutely connected and partially filled vesicles play an important role in determining the occurrence, movement and storage of ground water. These invariably form potential aquifers. The red-bole is non productive. In the alluvial areas, the occurrence of ground water is governed by sand/clay ratio. The sand beds generally form good aquifers, but due to the limited thickness and erratic occurrence in the form of lenses, the ground water structures in them are poor to moderately productive. The main source of recharge to the basaltic aquifer in the district is rainfall. Due to low permeabilities of basalts and undulating topography, the run-off is very high. This is reason for large scale seasonal fluctuation in the water level of the wells tapping trapeean formation. Ground Water in the Deccan Traps in Indore district²¹ occurs mostly under water table conditions. The nature of topography, extent and depth of weathering, distribution of secondary porosity in the form of fractures and joints and the occurrence and disposition of vesicular units govern the movement of ground water.

Sample collection and analysis : Groundwater samples from Indore²² were collected and analyzed for physico-chemical and bacteriological parameters. Figs. 5, 6, 7 and 8 depict the range of nitrate and faecal coliforms for Ahilya Nagar and Chandan Nagar²³ respectively in Indore.

Fig. 5. Nitrate concentration in groundwater samples of Ahilya Nagar, Indore.

Fig. 6. Faecal coliform concentration in groundwater samples of Ahilya Nagar, Indore.

Fig. 7. Nitrate concentration in groundwater samples of Chandan Nagar, Indore.

Fig. 8. Faecal coliform concentration in groundwater samples of Chandan Nagar, Indore.

In Ahilya Nagar, nitrate values were within the permissible limit for all the samples. However, all the samples were contaminated with faecal coliforms with maximum contamination found in monsoon⁴. Less contamination was encountered in summer. Some bore well samples were found to be contaminated with faecal coliforms even though they are located 40 m and 150 m (A4 and A5)

away from the community septic tank, respectively. In Chandan Nagar, nitrate values were within the permissible limit for both the seasons. Bore well sample C5 that was surrounded by 10–12 septic tanks consistently showed higher counts of faecal coliforms. However, dug well sample C6, collected from a house having 2 septic tanks at a distance of 6 m from the well showed minimum contamination. Except winter when the count was 16 CFU/100 ml, contamination is absent in the other seasons. Borewell sample C4, which is situated within the Mosque is contaminated only in monsoon (48 CFU/100 ml). The results in Ahilya Nagar of Indore reveal that contamination is present in bore well samples located as far as 150 m from the community septic tank. Since the region has hard rock and has secondary porosity in the form of fractures, leachate can travel longer distance.

Conclusion

Once groundwater is tapped as source of water supply, its protection becomes a top priority for the sustainable utilization. On-site sanitation can contaminate nearby water sources. Disease risks from drinking water infected with faecal coli and viral contaminants include hepatitis, poliomyelitis, diarrhoeal diseases, typhoid, dysentery and cholera. While the resource protection entails the assessment of water sources vulnerability and pollutant loading at the scale of an aquifer, the source protection requires the best practice measures that can be implemented around water source points. To guarantee a good quality water supply entails effort in many aspects ranging from borewell construction to demarcation of protection zones around a boreholes or open wells. However, on-site sanitation program should be discouraged in hard rock areas with shallow water table. Best engineering design should be ensured and operation and maintenance should be an integral part of the low-cost sanitation programs. Critical parameters like the depth of the water table, soil characteristics, and rock strata need to be considered in any program on installation of on-site sanitations where groundwater is used for drinking purpose. Operational monitoring of the functioning of on-site sanitation systems are important to verify comprehensively that human excreta and contaminants from sewage are not contaminating aquifers used for drinking-water abstraction. In addition to this regular monitoring of groundwater sources for ni-

trate and bacteriological parameters (faecal coliform) should be carried out in areas where on-site sanitation systems are in use. Appropriate hygiene education should be given to people using on-site sanitation systems. The concept of safe distance or sometimes termed optimum distance between drinking water supply wells and sources also needs to be considered for potential or existing pollution although it provides minimum protection measures against bacteria and viruses propagating from on-site sanitation systems. The concept of the minimum distance is related to a travel time that would ensure the decay of degradable contaminants like bacteria and viruses. It may also delay and dilute encroachment of non-degradable contaminants such as nitrate but cannot prevent their encroachment in the long-term. Unless water is extracted locally for domestic purposes, pollution of groundwater from on-site sanitation does no harm and is to be preferred to the considerable risks associated with defecation in the open. Where on-site sanitation would result in pollution of wells used for drinking-water, it is generally cheaper and easier to provide water from outside than to build sewers²⁴. This may require the closure of the previously used groundwater source, as use of untreated groundwater sources is common even when better quality alternatives are available^{25,26}. Best practice is to locate sewers outside drinking-water protection zones, although at some places lack of adequate area may be a problem owing to the small residential areas. Septic tanks must be emptied periodically, with controlling of the final sludge. Regular inspections should be performed to ascertain system effectiveness. The type and frequency of inspections should be determined by the size of the area, site conditions, resource sensitivity, the complexity and number of systems. Problem areas and areas likely to be at risk in the future be identified local sewage authorities to identify current and future service areas and determine treatment.

Legal frameworks : Regulatory agency need to be constituted in every city and taluka to look after sanitation and health issues. On-site system regulatory agency should look into, system selection and design, installation, maintenance, and monitoring of sanitation systems to protect an identified water resource, inspections during seasonal rises in ground water levels should be scheduled. Regulatory programs should be enacted as ordinances, management or local or state codes, or simply as guidelines.

Mandatory approval processes for constructing a designated system at a particular site based on site evaluation and system design and selection criteria should be framed. The criteria for proposed systems should be based on site conditions, wastewater characterization, anticipated flow, public health and resource protection goals and treatment technologies. An on-site wastewater compliance and enforcement program should be based on reasonable and scientifically defensible regulations. Process for reporting and responding to problems (e.g. complaint reporting, inspections) should be established. A system for issuing violation notices, compliance schedules, or fines, to address violations should be developed. It is necessary to ensure that on-site management issues are integrated into decisions regarding future growth and development.

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